

GREEN COMPOSITES FROM NATURAL FIBERS AND BACTERIAL BIOPLASTIC

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ABSTRACT

Green composites from natural/bio-fibers and bio-plastics are the wave of the future for designing eco-friendly novel materials especially for automotive applications. *Eco*-friendly green composites are fabricated from chopped natural fibers and a bacterial bioplastic, polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) through extrusion followed by injection molding processing. The bast fiber (hemp) based green composites showed improved stiffness while leaf (henequen) and fruit (coir) type natural fiber based composites showed improved toughness of the resulting green composites. The effect of hemp fiber concentration on tensile and impact properties of the resulting composites is investigated. The incorporation of 30 wt. % of hemp fiber in to the composite structure improves the modulus and impact strength of virgin “PHB” bioplastic by ~380 and 70% respectively. Around 100% improvement in impact strength of PHB biocomposite was observed with 30 wt. % reinforcement with rubberized coir fiber. The heat deflection temperature (HDT) of PHB biocomposite improved from 94 to 145⁰C after reinforcement with 30 wt. % hemp fiber. Fiber-matrix adhesion is evaluated through Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM) studies.

INTRODUCTION

Plastics are one of polymer chemistry’s greatest contributions to human welfare. Introduced to society approximately 60 years ago, plastics are characterized as malleable when heated, durable and capable of achieving a variety of performance parameters, depending on the formulation. However, the very property that makes plastics desirable i.e. their durability also makes disposal very difficult. Increasingly environmental awareness, societal concern and decreasing land fill space together provide the motivation to search for biopolymers as an alternative to traditional plastics¹⁻⁵. Biodegradable polymers are now moving into the mainstream economy. Studies predict that biopolymers that are biodegradable may soon be competing with commodity plastics⁶. The biodegradable polymer market in North America is estimated at 25 million pounds in 2000 and will increase to over 35 million pounds in 2005. The use of biopolymers from renewable resources is attaining increased importance and worlds leading industries and manufacturers seek to replace dwindling petrochemical-based feedstock with bio-based polymers/materials.

Biopolymers need to find new and emerging applications to make it possible for their large scale production in order to compete with the petroleum based traditional plastics. Poly (β -hydroxyalkanoate)s (PHAs), which are synthesized biochemically by microbial fermentation and which may be produced in the future by transgenic plants, represent natural polyesters. The 1st PHA (general chemical structure shown in scheme 1) discovered was poly (β -hydroxybutyrate) (PHB). The bioplastic PHB is a biochemically produced polyester that constitutes a carbon reserve in a wide variety of bacteria⁷ and has attracted much attention as a biodegradable thermoplastic polyester⁸⁻¹⁰. It can be degraded to water and carbon dioxide under environmental conditions by a variety of bacteria and has a large potential for applications of environmentally degradable plastics¹¹. However, it suffers from some disadvantages compared with conventional plastics, for example, brittleness and a narrow processability window¹². In order to improve these properties, various copolymers containing hydroxyalkanoate units other than 3-hydroxybutyrate (3HB) have been biosynthesized¹³, one best example being poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-

3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV). The bacterial polyesters PHB and PHBV present the advantages of biodegradability and biocompatibility over other thermoplastics with useful mechanical properties. However, their costs and performance must be adjusted by blending with suitable polymers or through fiber reinforcements.

To reduce vehicle weight; a shift away from steel alloys towards aluminum, plastics and composites has predicted that in near future polymer composites will comprise ~ 15% of a car weight²¹. Natural fiber composites are now emerging as the realistic alternative to glass-reinforced composites and automakers see the strong potential in making the auto-parts from bio-composites¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Natural fiber reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites are already in use by DaimlerChrysler¹⁵. The world's leading

Polyhydroxyalkanoate or "PHA"
when "R" is CH₃ it is called "PHB"

Scheme 1

The main motivation¹⁹ of using natural fibers to replace glass fibers is the low cost, low density (~ 1/2 of glass), acceptable specific strength properties, ease of separation, enhanced energy recovery, CO₂ sequestration, and biodegradability. Auto companies are seeking materials with sound abatement capability as well as reduced weight for fuel efficiency. Natural fibers possess excellent sound absorbing efficiency and are shatter resistant unlike glass fiber based composites. In automotive parts, compared to glass composites, natural fiber reinforced composites reduces the mass of the component, lowers the energy²⁰ needed for production by 80%. Automotive mass can be reduced by replacing steel and glass fiber composites (GRP)²² by natural fiber composites.

Industry figures show²³ that carmakers used 10,000 tons of bio-fiber in 2001 and it is estimated that demands of natural fibers would be in the hundreds of the thousands of tons by the end of the decade. Most of the bio-composites by the auto-industries now concentrate on natural fiber reinforced polypropylene composites. The demand for bio-plastic is likely to grow rapidly. Having 'green plastics' would be beneficial for the US automotive producers since recently, the European Union issued an 'end of vehicle life directive' which makes car manufacturers responsible for recycling cars at the end of their working lives, effective for new vehicles by the end of 2002 and for all cars by 2007. Natural resource based plastics are seen as the next legislative goal beyond recycling. In an on-going project to develop bio-based composite materials for next generation of green automotive applications, a group of researchers at Michigan State University are striving to generate a new generation of eco-friendly greener composite materials from natural fiber and bacterial polyester. This paper deals with fabrication and physico-mechanical properties evaluations of injection molded green composites from chopped natural fibers and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) bioplastic.

EXPERIMENTAL

The PHB used was in pellet form and obtained from Biomer, Germany. The PHB used here is plasticized PHB (proprietary to Biomer). The green hemp used was obtained from Flaxcraft, NJ. The henequen fiber was procured from Mexico while the rubberized coir was obtained from India. The chopped natural fibers (2 to 6 mm) were used for composite fabrication.

Processing

The PHB pellets and the chopped fibers used were pre-dried in a vacuum oven for 6-8 hours. The PHB and the chosen fiber were extruded together in a twin-screw extruder ZSK 30 (Werner-Pfleiderer). The extruder contains six temperature zones which are individually controlled. The zone temperatures used were set at 190°C-185°C-180°C-175°C-165°C-135°C respectively. The PHB pellets were fed through an automatic feeder, while the fiber was added manually. The fiber was added to the extruder through port 7, Scheme 2 illustrates schematic representation of the process.

Scheme 2: Schematic representation of Extruder configuration

The extruder speed was set at 100 rpm and the torque ranged from 40-60% throughout. The extruded material was cooled in a water bath and then pelletized for further injection molding.

The pellets extruded were dried in a vacuum oven and molded using an 85-ton Cincinnati-Milacron press. The injection molder has four temperature zones. These zones are the nozzle, and zones 1-3. These zones were maintained at 375°F-345°F-335°F-330°F, with a dye temperature of 75°F. The materials were injection molded as standard tensile coupons and subsequently used for mechanical and thermal testing.

Analysis and Testing

Injection molded samples were used for tensile, flexural and notched Izod impact tests. A United Calibration Corp. SFM – 20 machine was used for tensile and flexural testing. The tensile testing of the

Figure 1: Effect of hemp fiber amount on tensile properties of green composites (A: PHB; B: PHB + 15 wt.% hemp; C: PHB + 30 wt.% hemp)

bio-plastics and green/bio-composites was conducted using a load cell of 1000 lbs capacity. A preload of 2 lbs was used. The test speed was 0.2 inches/minute. The flexural testing of the bio-plastics and bio-composites was conducted using a 20 lbs load cell. A preload of 0.2 lbs was used and the test speed was 0.05 inches/minute in all the cases. For the impact tests, the injection molded tensile coupons were into 2.5"x0.5"x0.125" sized samples and 0.1" deep notches were cut into the sample beams using a TMI notch cutter. Notched Izod impact testing was performed on a Testing Machines Inc. 43-02-01

Monitor/Impact. A 5 ft-lb pendulum was used to impact the samples.

Heat Deflection Temperature Measurement

Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT) was determined using a TA instruments 2980 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) as per ASTM D 648 standard. HDT is a measure of the temperature at which a material deflects by 0.25 mm under the application of a load. The load used can be either 66 psi or 624 psi. In the present case a load value of 66 psi was used. The injection molded tensile coupons were cut so that the samples were 2.15”x0.5”x0.125” to accommodate the DMA. For determining the heat deflection temperature, a constant load of 66 psi was applied at the center of a 3-point bending sample and heated at the rate of 2°C per minute from room temperature to desired temperature (120 to 170°C). The sample deflection was recorded as a function of temperature.

Figure 2: Effect of hemp fiber amount on tensile properties of green composites (A: PHB; B: PHB + 15 wt.% hemp; C: PHB + 30 wt.% hemp)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through effective reinforcement of bioplastic with inexpensive cellulosic natural fibers, value-added biocomposite/green composite materials are poised to enhance the sustainability of the new materials²⁴. However extensive research and development is required to find best formulations and processing conditions to reach at the targeted composite materials of industrial attractions. The present studies highlight our investigations on use of various natural fibers like a bast fiber hemp e.g. green hemp

Figure 3: Tensile properties comparison (A: PHB; B: PHB+ 30 wt.% hemp; C: PHB + 30 wt.% henequen; D: PHB + 30 wt.% rubberized coir)

unlike usual retted natural fibers; a leaf fiber e.g. henequen and a fruit fiber e.g. coir on the performance of the green composites as made through usual extrusion followed by injection molding processing. Figure 1 illustrates the effect of variation of hemp fiber content on the tensile properties of the green composites. The tensile modulus of virgin bioplastic (PHB) improves by 288% and 377% when reinforced with 15 and 30 wt.% of hemp fiber respectively. However fiber reinforcement does not improve the tensile strength of the virgin PHB bioplastic. Research into effective surface modifications of natural fibers and use of specific coupling agent is on

progress to improve the tensile strength properties of the resulting green composites. As it is well-known; PHB is a brittle polymer and thus research to produce a high impact PHB has attracted the attention of researchers. As depicted in Fig. 2 on natural fiber reinforcement the impact strength of PHB improves and with 30 wt. % hemp reinforcement we observe around 70% enhancement of impact strength of virgin PHB bioplastic.

In our previously published research²⁵ we have observed that bast fiber based biocomposites exhibit improved stiffness while leaf fiber based biocomposites exhibit superior impact properties. The fruit fibers like coir fiber based composites are poised to exhibit low stiffness and high impact properties. In our present investigation we took rubberized coir with a goal of achieving improved impact behavior of the green/bio-composites. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate a comparative tensile and impact behavior of 3 different types of natural fiber based green composites. As expected the bast fiber (hemp) based composites showed improved stiffness and lower impact strength as compared to leaf (henequen) and fruit (coir) fiber based green composites. Coir (rubberized) based green composites also exhibited inferior stiffness over henequen based counterparts. Although rubberized coir based green composite is expected to exhibit much improved toughness over hemp and even henequen based green composites we have not observed an improvement in impact strength the reason of which is yet to be established.

Figure 4: Impact properties comparison (A: PHB; B: PHB+ 30 wt.% hemp; C: PHB + 30 wt.% henequen; D: PHB + 30 wt.% rubberized coir)

Heat deflection temperature (HDT) is an important parameter when a material is being used for

Figure 5: HDT of: (A) PHB; B: PHB + 15 wt. % hemp; C: PHB + 30 wt. % hemp

high temperature structural applications. Our goal is to use PHB-based green composites in automotive parts applications. The heat deflection temperatures of PHB and its green composites are represented in Figure 5. It can be seen that with the addition of 15 wt. % hemp fiber the HDT of PHB improves from 94 to 124⁰C where as 30 wt.% hemp reinforcements improves the HDT to 145⁰C thus we achieve more than 50% enhancement of HDT over the virgin bioplastic.

As a part of our present investigations we also looked in to the fiber-matrix adhesion behavior of the green composites. Fiber-matrix adhesion plays an important role in controlling the over all performance of the composite materials. Figure 6 is the Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy pictures of tensile fractured surfaces of the hemp-PHB and coir-PHB based green composites. Fiber pull-out is observed in the case of coir based composites thus indicating very poor adhesion of coir and PHB.

Figure 6: ESEM pictures of tensile fractured surfaces of (a) hemp-PHB composites, 500 X, Scale: 100 μm (b) coir-PHB composites, 300 X, Scale: 150 μm

From the ESEM we also observe that coir is a very coarse fiber unlike hemp fiber. Although we observe better fiber fiber-matrix interactions in case of hemp based composites, an improvement in adhesion through fiber surface modifications/use of new coupling agent and optimized processing conditions is required to design high strength and superior performance green composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The major drawbacks of most of the currently marketed biodegradable polymers including the polyhydroxyalkanoates are their high costs. It is encouraging that cost-effective green composites can be produced from expensive bioplastics through reinforcement with inexpensive natural/bio-fibers. The emergence of new applications for green composites will produce large-scale demand for bioplastics, which would help in a long run in reducing their cost. Recent advances in natural fiber development, biodegradable polymers, and composite science offer significant opportunities to design and engineer improved value-added materials with enhanced support of global sustainability. By embedding inexpensive natural fibers in biodegradable thermoplastic PHB, value-added green composite materials are developed. The usual conventional processing techniques like extrusion and injection molding can be applied for processing these green materials. The tensile modulus of the virgin bioplastic improves by more than 375% on reinforcement with 30 wt. % hemp fiber. Among all the natural fibers studied (green hemp, henequen and rubberized coir), the coir-based composites showed the best impact strength (~100% improvement of impact strength with 30 wt.% rubberized coir). Bast fiber (hemp) based green composites showed improved stiffness over leaf (henequen) and fruit (coir) based green composites while we observe the reverse in impact properties. Heat deflection temperature of virgin PHB bioplastic improved from 94 to 145⁰C with 30 wt. % hemp fiber reinforcement thus improving the thermal properties of the green

composites. Effective surface modifications of natural fibers, use of new coupling agent, hybridization of fibers (combination of bast/leaf/fruit fiber in appropriate proportions), and optimized processing conditions are still under constant investigations to design superior performance green composites for 21st century automotive applications.

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